

EDUCATION FUNDING AND TEACHER MIGRATION: THE UNENDING CHALLENGES OF DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 30

Issue 10

Pages: 1538-1544

Document ID: 2025PEMJ2929

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14663077

Manuscript Accepted: 12-31-2024

Education Funding and Teacher Migration: The Unending Challenges of Developing Countries

Juvelito B. Veliganio,* Regina P. Galigao
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study examines the issues and concerns of developing countries about education particularly on the aspect of education funding and teacher migration. The study is conducted using document analysis and data mining methods. The various education policies and programs of developing countries worldwide were examined and analyzed. There are at least three (3) developing countries from each continent subjected to the study. The data gathered from each country were compared by identifying the similarities and dissimilarities in its educational system. The result of the analysis reveals that education funding in developing countries is critical in ensuring quality education that is accessible to all. However, issues such as ineffective management of funding appropriation and allocation from the government and school leaders are prevalent in some countries. Furthermore, teacher migration to more developed countries becomes a contemporary challenge experienced by developing nations that need to be addressed by each government through targeted interventions, school programs, and policies. Overall, the study revealed that the role of education funding from the government or private sector is significant for developing countries to improve their educational system, promote teacher satisfaction, and increase student achievements.

Keywords: *educational policies, school management, developing countries, quality education, teacher migration*

Introduction

The United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) established the framework for the sustainable goal of 2030, which reaffirms the role of the government in implementing policies and programs for education. The framework ensures equitable and quality education and promotes lifelong learning opportunities for all. Education is an integral factor that helps the growth and development of a nation. The educational system of developing countries is one of the equalizers that supports nations to create an edge amidst disparities of wealth and income. However, along with the improvement in curricular programs and educational practices, developing countries have continued experiencing challenges and issues. These issues are creating complex problems that cannot be dealt with by the government alone. Education funding has become a primary concern for poor nations. The fast-growing educational trends across the globe created a disparity between rich and poor countries in terms of quality and accessibility.

Secondly, the problem of teacher migration also the educational system of developing countries. This problem of migration of teachers can be internal or external. A transfer of teachers from private school to public school or from both to another country resulted in a brain drain. The exodus of teachers to another country is stimulated by better opportunities abroad or a lack of opportunities in their homeland (Ndiangui, 2021).

Based on studies, many teachers migrate due to low salaries, poor working conditions, and the lack of professional development in their mother countries. Aside from these, factors such as school leadership and lack of school infrastructure have contributed to the departure of teachers abroad (Gonzales, 2021). This issue of migration has created a deeper problem in the education system of developing countries. Most of the teachers leaving their countries to work overseas are some of the most qualified and experienced in their field. This scenario has developed an imbalance in schools since new and inexperienced educators will fill vacancies. This imbalance will be an additional burden to the government and school management as the cycle continues. Thus, as revealed in some studies, it will affect student performance and achievements

Research Objectives

The aim is to derive some general conclusions about the design, implementation, and diffusion of best practices and the strategies and interventions of developing countries in facing the challenges of education. In addition, this research will provide answers for the following aims:

1. Analyze the impact of education funding and teacher migration to developing countries on their educational system.
2. Compare the different practices and strategies of developing countries in coping with education funding and teacher migration.

Literature Review

This study is anchored to the Equity Theory of education proposed by John Stacey Adams in 1960. The theory suggests that fair distribution of resources is essential for social justice and equity. Thus, it is directly associated with issues concerning the developing countries which are the access to equitable & quality education and teacher migration. In past years, a disparity of funding between rich and poor countries has created an economic gap that resulted in unequal opportunities among students and teachers (Madani, 2019). Funding for education is a major problem in many developing countries and has influenced the way education is being implemented.

To minimize the disparity problem, some countries recourse to partnerships with private institutions and international aid to ensure that quality education is being offered. These partnerships have resulted in both good and unsuccessful outcomes for some countries due to mismanagement and corruption (Schomaker, 2020). Despite the shortcomings, the role of the government in providing support to education is still considered integral and essential. The availability of a budget allocation and appropriation to improve the educational system is the prime responsibility of the government to its people. Nonetheless, governments in developing countries are also trying their best to provide education for all but their capacity is limited. These limitations have contributed to the existence of other macro problems that affect education.

Additionally, teacher migration has also impacted the education system of developing countries. In many cases, the departure of these teachers has affected the quality and substantiality of education in schools where these teachers came from. Consequently, this also affects student achievement and motivation (Ekmekci & Serrano, 2022). Therefore, the government and education sector of developing countries should implement strategies and policies to mitigate the effect of teacher migration to education. These mitigations include training, more benefits, competitive salaries, and a good working environment.

With the issues and challenges faced by developing countries, a more progressive and developmental approach from the government must be done to keep education in developing countries at par with other countries in terms of competitiveness, teacher quality, and employment of graduates. A more sustainable and comprehensive program must be cascaded by the government with the collaboration of the private sector to ensure effective management.

Methodology

An explanatory mixed-method research approach was used to study the different issues and concerns of developing countries across the globe about education. Text mining and sentiment analysis are applied exclusively to policy papers, reports, and academic literature of different education programs and policies of the identified countries. Three (3) developing countries from each continent were chosen as subjects of the study. An analysis was conducted to identify similarities and comparisons between policies and programs implemented. Qualitative data is then used to validate and provide context for the data mined.

Results and Discussion

This study aimed to gather data on the different issues and concerns of developing countries across the globe about education. We collated and analyzed the gathered data to develop more sustainable information on issues concerning.

Education Funding and Management

The process of funding the educational system worldwide greatly affects the country's socio-economic status. A certain allocation from the national budget must be periodically appropriated to improve education. It should be religiously done to provide quality and inclusive education for its citizens. As a basic right of every individual, it is believed that education will provide an opportunity for human beings to live a dignified life (DE, 2022).

Public-Private Partnerships

Public-private partnerships are collaborative agreements between the government and non-government organizations on the sharing of resources, expertise, and educational outcomes to improve the educational quality of a certain country. In some contexts, it is noted that schools, under PPP programs, generate more innovations in instruction, pedagogy, and technology (Verger et al., 2021). However, more training and professional development activities must be extended to teachers to fully implement the goals of partnerships.

Table 1. *Public-Private Partnerships*

<i>Countries</i>	<i>Reasons</i>
Nigeria	The existence of perennial issues of corruption and mismanagement hinders the procurement of allocation from private partners. Thus, it affects the delivery of needed services to different schools, colleges, and universities. It is also shown that poor government commitment affects funding and resource allocation. However, despite these derailing, the advantages of PPP outweigh the negative variables (Barrera-Osorio et al., 2022).
Pakistan	A country in South Asia with a high illiteracy rate, Pakistan is striving to improve its educational system. The existence of PPP has helped the country ensure that its teachers receive skill training and professional development to improve their performance. Thus, the availability of trained teachers helps the regions of Pakistan to increase literacy rates across the country (Kalim, U., & Bibi, 2022).
Egypt	The implementation of PPP for education in Egypt has been effective due to some critical factors. These factors are financial, political, legal, and managerial. Among the given factors, managerial and operational factors were considered the relevant aspect that helps in the successful implementation of Public Private Partnership. It means that people trusted how partnership for education is being handled and implemented by the sectors involved (Helmy et al., 2020).

The existence of Public-Private Partnerships in Nigeria, Pakistan, and Egypt manifests a successful implementation of the program. This success is attributed to effective management and monitoring of the program. The three countries mentioned that PPP has improved education outcomes, more access to quality education, and the professional development of teachers. Thus, PPP also contributes to the political and economic stability of these countries (Almeile et al., 2024).

Government Support to Education

The role of government in education is crucial to the development of a certain nation. Creating educated citizens would contribute to a more competitive and productive workforce. Thus, it is the inherent responsibility of the government to provide quality education as a means of promoting economic growth and development. Therefore, the government should provide equitable education to people from primary to tertiary (Farayibi, A. O., & Folarin, O., 2021).

Table 2. *Government Support to Education*

<i>Countries</i>	<i>Reasons</i>
Indonesia	In the past decades, Indonesia has been able to solve issues on equitable access to education. The government allocated an annual budget intended to support education, student learning, and teacher training. The Education 2025 program of the country is aimed to minimize and eliminate illiteracy in the country. However, the most difficult challenge of the Indonesian educational system is the rapid curricular changes in the world. Thus, the achievement of quality and competitive education is the nation's current priority (Sukmayadi, V., & Yahya, A., 2020).
Uzbekistan	Uzbekistan is experiencing a tremendous challenge in its educational system. Several programs and reforms are being implemented but are proven to be ineffective in solving issues in education. These issues include the progressive development of curriculum from primary to tertiary, the lack of standardized entrance examinations in college programs, and the minimal support for education and research from the government (Eshchanova et al., 2020).
Chile	In Chile, education reforms have made schooling become more privatized and localized due to policy changes and market-oriented innovations. This evolution of school management has created an adverse effect on government implementation of state policies and regulations. Thus, allowing a more unregulated market for education may result in the negligence of professional skills and development (Bellei & Munoz, 2023).

Chile, Indonesia, and Uzbekistan have implemented educational and curriculum reforms to improve their educational system. However, these countries have experienced some setbacks due to rapid changes in global education. These setbacks and downsides may affect the quality of graduates and the future workforce of these nations. Although the government provided support to improve compulsory education in both countries, its effective implementation is limited. A thorough improvement in teacher training and wide government investment in education is needed (Shaturayev, 2021). Together with the training, the availability of better school infrastructures and learning environments is also needed.

School Environment and Infrastructure

School environment and infrastructure are necessities that should be prioritized by school leaders and administration. A conducive school environment improves learning outcomes and teaching performance (Yangambi, 2023). These include spacious classrooms, well-equipped laboratories, and other facilities that improve student services. It is also established that the availability of a good learning environment contributes to the well-being and achievement of learners (AHMAD, 2020). These facilities will also help teachers deliver the content to the learners with the help of technology and other infrastructures.

Table 3. *School Environment and Infrastructure*

<i>Countries</i>	<i>Reasons</i>
Malaysia	The availability of good school infrastructure and technology in an educational institution is very essential. In Indonesian schools, it was revealed that these factors have improved learners' performance and the quality of the school's curricular program. However, it is also noted that infrastructure and technology can best help ensure quality education if they are proportionally distributed according to the needs of learners (Nurabadi et al., 2020).
Albania	The government is one of the countries in the world that declares its commitment to attaining UNESCO's goal, Education for All. However, similar to many developing countries, they experienced disparity of results, especially on international assessments. In the past year, many students scored below during the PISA 2018. This poor performance is attributed to the poor school environment and lack of school infrastructure to support quality education (Shahini, 2021).
Mexico	The presence of good school infrastructure and technological innovations in Mexican schools has a positive impact on their education system. Based on the report, the availability of infrastructure and technology ensures the quality of education in Mexico. A thorough transformation of the teaching-learning process in Mexican universities allows a more effective pedagogy of learning that benefits the students (Rodríguez-Abitia et al., 2020).

School infrastructure is an essential aspect of ensuring quality education. However, issues like educational disparity, less budget allocation, and geographical concerns hinder the full implementation of policies and programs about school infrastructures and technology innovation. This difficulty is usually observed in developing countries that are continuously striving to achieve excellence in education. (Nurhayati, 2021).

Distinct Point/s

The sub-variables of funding for education have one distinct point: (1) Management of funds.

Management of Funds

The intention of having a public-private partnership is to minimize the burden of government in providing support to education on a full scale. The PPP allows the government to improve education quality with the help of other sectors. However, the implementation

of PPP in other countries has proven to be ineffective due to mismanagement. One of the many risks is the lack of implementing policies and guidelines that ensure the success of the PPP. These policies will certainly help the government achieve success and the desired outcome of the partnership (Verger et al., 2021).

Table 4. *Distinct Points*

Countries		Reasons
Ghana	Limited Government help to private education	Management of private schools in Ghana is experiencing drawbacks such as a decline in enrolment. The government's authority to help private schools is being constrained by state laws and policies. With this, private school leaders have created intervention policies to overcome the issues of management. These include fundraising activities, strengthening faculty skills, and offering lower tuition (Salifu, 2022).
Argentina	Privatization of schools	De-institutionalization or privatization of schools in Argentina involves a long-term process, especially in the transition from public education. This approach might create a longer effect on educational management, especially on funding and budget allocation. This idea may appear to be permanent but a shift in political perspective might reverse the process (Díaz Ríos, 2019).
Ukraine	Misallocation of funds for education	Many countries in the Balkan Region, particularly Ukraine have experienced challenges in mismanagement of funds for education. The political struggle has caused the country to struggle against misappropriation of funds and ineffective utilization. These issues have bad effects on the country's desire to offer quality education (Sokol & Melko, 2022).

Education as an investment is crucial to the growth and development of a certain country. However, one of the challenges experienced by developing countries is how to implement effective and efficient educational policies for their people. A good education will ensure that the graduates are globally competitive and work-ready (Madani, 2019).

Teacher Migration

Teacher migration is a continuous occurrence in developing countries. The best teachers are leaving their hometowns to work abroad. Teacher migration happens for many reasons such as salary, professional development, and job satisfaction. Furthermore, teacher migration has also a great influence on the behavior and achievements of learners when suddenly left by teachers due to transfer or migration (Harrell et al., 2019).

Teachers' Professional Development

The role of teachers in the educational process is very essential. Teaching is considered as one of the noblest professions. However, being a teacher is also a great responsibility since you need to possess the attributes of a great educator. One of the attributes is the qualification and skills in teaching. Teachers with better skills and qualifications are more likely to contribute to the achievements of learners. Hence, a more capable teacher can share better knowledge with learners (Lee, S. W., & Lee, E. A., 2020)

Table 5. *Teachers' Professional Development*

Countries		Reasons
Philippines		The Philippines is one of the many countries in the world that is facing problems in education. The flight of teachers from private schools to public schools and the migration of teachers from both private and public schools to other countries. This local and international migration is steamed from low salaries and benefits, lack of professional and educational development, and the impact of leadership styles of school leaders. This phenomenon has greatly affect learners achievements and performance (Gonzales, 2021)
South Africa		Teacher migration in South Africa has been a long-term challenge to the government. Many of their teachers transferred to other countries for better opportunities. One of the reasons for local and international migration is the poor working conditions of the schools and the lack of professional development for teachers. This migration has resulted in a shortage of teachers especially in the rural areas of the country (Mlambo & Adetiba, 2020)
Zimbabwe		Similar to many developing countries, the migration of teachers has brought hope to many educators from Zimbabwe to earn better salaries abroad. However, they also experience some setbacks during their stay. One of the challenges is the lack of job security and the short and indefinite contracts given to them. Even with this situation, these teachers continue to stay and work abroad (Weda & de Villiers, 2019)

The impact of teacher migration on the state of education in countries like the Philippines, South Africa, and Zimbabwe is very significant. Low salaries and lesser professional development have caused teachers to migrate to other work and other countries. However, the Philippines is also experiencing the dual migration effect of teacher migration from private schools to public high schools and from both sectors to other countries. Thus, the brain –drain of professional teachers has affected our educational system.

Teachers' Workload

Teachers are one of the most overworked professions in the world. Their work does not only include teaching but also some administrative work beyond their job descriptions. This typical scenario often exists in schools in developing countries.

Teachers are often given more teaching with additional administrative tasks that result in teacher burnout. Teacher burnout due to the bulk of assignments has a significant effect on the performance and achievement of learners (Jomuad, 2021).

Table 6. Teachers' Workload and Assignment

<i>Countries</i>	<i>Reasons</i>
Philippines	The Second Congressional Commission on Education (EDCOM II) report states that many teachers in the Philippines are burdened by administrative tasks not related to the teaching profession. It is also noted that many teachers in Basic Education are teaching subjects that are related to their majors in college. These challenges have created an impact on teachers' workload and assignments. However, some studies reveal that workloads only affect the preparation of teaching materials and the supervision of learners (Pacaol, 2021)
El Salvador	The government of El Salvador is trying to integrate social-emotional learning in education as a comprehensive intervention for teachers' well-being. This idea was introduced as a response to the high stress level and emotional exhaustion of teachers (Soares, 2024). These factors are experienced due to teachers' exposure to difficult teaching workloads and assignments.

The Philippine government has finally recognized the limitations of our education system, especially in the Basic Education department. The Second Congressional Commission on Education (EDCOM II) has seen through these challenges, especially on the workloads of our teachers. Similarly, El Salvador also experiences similar issues in their education. With this, both are separately working to enhance the status of their teachers and have provided mental and emotional support to teaching personnel experiencing burnout and stress.

Teachers' Salaries and Benefits

Job satisfaction is one of the innate tendencies that motivates employees to stay loyal and dedicated to work. This factor needs to be taken into consideration by industries, companies, educational institutions, and the government. Many studies reveal working conditions, salaries, and benefits of workers are the major factors affecting their performance. Similar to educational institutions, teachers' salaries and benefits are determinants of their satisfaction (Sahito & Vaisanen, 2020).

Table 7. Teachers' Salaries and Benefits

<i>Countries</i>	<i>Reasons</i>
Pakistan	Pakistan is a thriving country in South Asia working to enhance its educational system by making necessary modifications, enhancements, and innovations to its curriculum and teachers. One of the greatest leaps made by Pakistan in educational reform is trying to increase the salaries and wages of teachers through performance pay. According to the study, the result reveals that the existence of performance pay to teachers doubled the achievements of students (Brown & Andrabi, 2020).
Philippines	Many studies were conducted to determine the correlations between teacher performance and job satisfaction. Results of these studies reveal that teachers with high levels of job satisfaction perform better in their work. However, other factors, such as the supervision of school heads and additional work may also affect teachers' satisfaction (Baluyos et al., 2019)
Indonesia	Teachers' salaries and compensation have been a predictor of teachers' performance in other countries. In a study conducted in Indonesia, it was revealed that aside from salary and benefits, factors like school culture and school leadership have a significant effect on teachers' performance (Kanya et al., 2021). Another study suggests that job security, working conditions, and principals leadership affect teachers' performance (Wea et al., 2020)

The three countries are working to improve their educational system to ensure quality and competitive education. However, Pakistan needs to improve its curriculum and the compensation of its teachers. Further, it revealed that in countries like Pakistan and the Philippines, salary is the sole predictor of teacher satisfaction. Other factors like working conditions and school leadership play a significant role in teachers' satisfaction.

Distinct Point/s

The sub-variables of teacher migration have one distinct point: (1) Intervention Strategy.

Interventions to Retain Teachers

Despite the efforts of governments from developing countries to stop or minimize the migration of teachers, their intervention capacity is limited. Furthermore, it is also a general fact that teacher retention does not have a one-size-fits-all solution. Hence, other factors such as dissatisfaction and personal desire of teachers may also influence their migration (Holmes et al., 2019)

Table 8. Distinct Points

<i>Countries</i>	<i>Reasons</i>
Gambia	Clustering of Schools Gambia designed an intervention focusing on the improvement of teachers. This intervention includes a ready to teach lesson plans, the presence of teaching assistants, and the consistent mentoring of teachers. This strategy promises a better result for the endeavor of Gambian education (Eble et al., 2021).
Bangladesh	Poor Managerial Intervention Unlike other developing countries, Bangladesh has experienced a poor educational system that resulted in continued unequal access to quality education for all. This issue includes the poor working conditions of teachers in universities that influenced them to transfer. The situation is also a product of poor managerial intervention from school leaders. Thus, this scenario has continued to affect the quality of education in the country, especially in higher education.

Gambia has implemented a teacher-centered approach to improve classroom instruction by providing them with ready-made lesson plans, teaching assistants, and mentoring programs. Bangladesh, on the other hand, faces more complex issues such as inequitable access to education, poor school infrastructure, and ineffective school leadership. While Gambia's approach is progressive, Bangladesh

needs a more comprehensive reform to address complex problems. Nonetheless, both countries are doing their best to improve the quality of education.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the study reveals the interconnectedness of factors affecting the educational systems of developing countries. Based on the data mining, education funding plays a critical role in ensuring quality education that is accessible for all. However, effective and efficient management should accompany budget appropriation and allocation both from the government and from school leaders. Furthermore, teacher migration from developing countries to highly developed countries is seen to be increasing due to low compensation and benefits. Hence, this challenge also needs to be addressed by each government through targeted interventions, education programs, and policies. Overall, the improvement of education in developing countries requires a better approach through sustainable investments that consider the diverse needs of students and teachers.

References

AHMAD, D. F. Infrastructure and the New Education Policy 2020.

Almeile, A. M., Chipulu, M., Ojiako, U., Vahidi, R., & Marshall, A. (2024). Project-focussed literature on public-private partnership (PPP) in developing countries: a critical review. *Production Planning & Control*, 35(7), 683-710.

Baluyos, G. R., Rivera, H. L., & Baluyos, E. L. (2019). Teachers' job satisfaction and work performance. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 7(8), 206-221.

Barrera-Osorio, F., Blakeslee, D. S., Hoover, M., Linden, L., Raju, D., & Ryan, S. P. (2022). Delivering education to the underserved through a public-private partnership program in Pakistan. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 104(3), 399-416.

Bellei, C., & Munoz, G. (2023). Models of regulation, education policies, and changes in the education system: a long-term analysis of the Chilean case. *Journal of Educational Change*, 24(1), 49-76.

Brown, C., & Andrabi, T. (2020). Inducing positive sorting through performance pay: Experimental evidence from Pakistani schools. University of California at Berkeley Working Paper.

DE, U. (2022). EDUCATION FUNDING SYSTEM.

Díaz Ríos, C. (2019). Domestic coalitions in the variation of education privatization: an analysis of Chile, Argentina, and Colombia. *Journal of Education Policy*, 34(5), 647-668.

Eble, A., Frost, C., Camara, A., Bouy, B., Bah, M., Sivaraman, M., & Elbourne, D. (2021). How much can we remedy very low learning levels in rural parts of low-income countries? Impact and generalizability of a multi-pronged para-teacher intervention from a cluster-randomized trial in The Gambia. *Journal of development economics*, 148, 102539.

Ekmekci, A., & Serrano, D. M. (2022). The impact of teacher quality on student motivation, achievement, and persistence in science and mathematics. *Education Sciences*, 12(10), 649.

Eshchanova, R., Bekchanova, D., & Bobojonovaa, G. (2020). THE CURRENT CORE OF EDUCATION REFORMS IN UZBEKISTAN: ONE STEP FORWARD TWO STEPS BACK?. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 8(2056-5852), 169-182.

Farayibi, A. O., & Folarin, O. (2021). Does government education expenditure affect educational outcomes? New evidence from sub-Saharan African countries. *African Development Review*, 33(3), 546-559.

Gonzales, N. J. (2021). Migration from private to public institutions: A phenomenological study on transitional challenges from teachers' viewpoints. *Migration*, 1(2).

Harrell, P. E., Thompson, R., & Brooks, K. (2019). Leaving schools behind: The impact of school student body and working conditions on teacher retention and migration. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 30(2), 144-158.

Helmy, R., Khourshed, N., Wahba, M., & Bary, A. A. E. (2020). Exploring critical success factors for public Public-Private Partnership cases

Holmes, B., Parker, D., & Gibson, J. (2019). Rethinking teacher retention in hard-to-staff schools.

Jomuad, P. D., Antiquina, L. M. M., Cericos, E. U., Bacus, J. A., Vallejo, J. H., Dionio, B. B., ... & Clarin, A. S. (2021). Teachers' workload in relation to burnout and work performance. *International journal of educational policy research and review*.

Kalim, U., & Bibi, S. (2022). A review of public-private partnership for elevating the literacy rate in Pakistan. *Journal of Social Sciences Advancement*, 3(2), 92-97.

Lee, S. W., & Lee, E. A. (2020). Teacher qualification matters: The association between cumulative teacher qualification and students'

educational attainment. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 77, 102218.

Madani, R. A. (2019). Analysis of educational quality, a goal of education for all policy. *Higher Education Studies*, 9(1), 100-109.

Mlambo, V. H., & Adetiba, T. C. (2020). The brain drain of teachers in South Africa: Identifying the dynamics of its push factors. *e-BANGI*, 17(1), 152-164.

Ndiangu, P. (2021). From brain drain to brain gain: the battle against talent drain. *Journal of Culture and Values in Education*, 4(1), 34-48.

Nurabadi, A., Bafadal, I., Priyatni, E. T., & Gunawan, I. (2020, December). Analysis of the availability of school facilities and infrastructure as an effort to accelerate school quality improvement. In *6th International Conference on Education and Technology (ICET 2020)* (pp. 89-92). Atlantis Press.

Nurhayati, L. (2021). Policy Effectiveness Program for Improving Education Equality through the Development of Education Facilities and Infrastructure.

Pacaol, N. (2021). Teacher's Workload Intensification: A Qualitative Case Study of Its Implications on Teaching Quality. *International Online Journal of Education and Teaching*, 8(1), 43-60.

Rodríguez-Abitia, G., Martínez-Pérez, S., Ramirez-Montoya, M. S., & Lopez-Caudana, E. (2020). Digital gap in universities and challenges for quality education: A diagnostic study in Mexico and Spain. *Sustainability*, 12(21), 9069.

Sahito, Z., & Vaisanen, P. (2020). A literature review on teachers' job satisfaction in developing countries: Recommendations and solutions for the enhancement of the job. *Review of Education*, 8(1), 3-34.

Salifu, I. (2022). State-funded secondary education policy: Implications for private school management in Ghana. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*, 21(4), 719-732.

Schomaker, R. M. (2020). Conceptualizing corruption in public private partnerships. *Public Organization Review*, 20(4), 807-820.

Shahini, A. (2021). Inequalities in Albanian education: Evidence from large-scale assessment studies. *Kultura i Edukacija*, 4 (134), 40-70.

Shaturaev, J. (2021). A comparative analysis of public education system of Indonesia and Uzbekistan. *Bioscience Biotechnology Research Communications*, 14(5), 89-92.

Soares Jones, F. (2024). The effects of adding social-emotional learning to a comprehensive education intervention in El Salvador on teacher well-being: a mixed methods evaluation.

Sokol, T., & Melko, L. (2022). Current challenges of higher education in Ukraine. *Pedagogy and education management review*, (1), 49-53.

Sukmayadi, V., & Yahya, A. (2020). Indonesian education landscape and the 21st century challenges. *Journal of Social Studies Education Research*, 11(4), 219-234.

Verger, A., Moschetti, M. C., & Fontdevila, C. (2021). How and why policy design matters: understanding the diverging effects of public-private partnerships in education. In *Realizing the Abidjan Principles on the Right to Education* (pp. 157-188). Edward Elgar Publishing.

Wea, D., Werang, B. R., Asmaningrum, H. P., & Irianto, O. (2020). Teachers' working conditions and job performance in the elementary schools of Indonesia: A survey from Southern Papua. *The International Journal of Educational Organization and Leadership*, 27(1), 37.

Weda, Z., & de Villiers, R. (2019). Migrant Zimbabwean teachers in South Africa: Challenging and rewarding issues. *Journal of International Migration and Integration*, 20, 1013-1028.

Yangambi, M. (2023). Impact of school infrastructures on students learning and performance: case of three public schools in a developing country. *Creative Education*, 14(4), 788-809.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Juvelito B. Veliganio

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Regina P. Galigao

Cebu Technological University – Philippines